

A CONCEPTUAL REPLICATION STUDY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-LEADERSHIP, GOAL COMMITMENT, AND PROBLEM-SOLVING ABILITY IN NURSING STUDENTS AT A SINGLE UNIVERSITY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18429534>

How to cite this Article: Yu-Kyung Park. (2026). A Conceptual Replication Study on The Relationship Between Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability In Nursing Students At A Single University. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 13(2), 201–207.

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Article Received on 31/12/2025

Article Revised on 22/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Purpose This study aimed to reconfirm the relationships among variables and verify the reliability of previous research findings through a conceptual replication study examining the associations between self-leadership, goal commitment, and problem-solving ability in nursing students. Recently, the nursing education environment in Korea has faced new challenges due to rapid expansion of student enrollment driven by national nursing workforce policies, resulting in increased heterogeneity within student populations. As disparities in major adaptation and learning motivation among students have intensified, a re-examination of factors related to the development of core competencies has become increasingly necessary. **Methods** A survey was conducted with 201 nursing students enrolled in a nursing program at a university located in U City. Data were collected using the Revised Self-Leadership Questionnaire (RSLQ), a goal commitment scale, and a problem-solving ability scale. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and Pearson's correlation analysis. **Results** Self-leadership ($r = .54, p < .001$) and goal commitment ($r = .53, p < .001$) showed statistically significant positive correlations with problem-solving ability. Analysis of differences according to general characteristics indicated that all three variables differed significantly by academic year, academic achievement, major satisfaction, and interpersonal relationships. Notably, the group with higher academic achievement showed significantly higher correlations across all competency indicators ($p < .01$). **Conclusion** This study strengthened theoretical credibility by demonstrating that the relationships among variables identified in previous research can be stably reproduced within a controlled, single-institution environment. The findings reconfirm the importance of non-cognitive assets such as self-leadership and goal commitment in relation to nursing students' problem-solving competence. The results particularly suggest the need for educational support that considers competency stagnation during the sophomore year and differences according to academic achievement levels.

KEYWORDS Nursing Students, Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, Problem-Solving Ability, Conceptual Replication Study.

I. INTRODUCTION**1. Need for the Study**

The core competency required by the nursing profession in modern society lies in problem-solving ability, which enables effective resolution of problems arising in complex clinical environments.^{[1][2]} Among the psychological factors related to self-efficacy that form the foundation of such professional competency, self-leadership determines self-directed learning attitudes,

while goal commitment reflects firm psychological commitment to academic and professional goals.^{[1][3]} These variables function as key non-cognitive factors that predict nursing students' academic achievement and ultimate professional competency development.^[1,4]

Recently, with the expansion of nursing department enrollment quotas, some universities have faced declining academic achievement and learning difficulties

among students as major issues in educational settings.^{[5][4]} Such learning difficulties are more likely to stem from deficiencies in non-cognitive regulatory competencies, such as the ability to lead one's own learning or set and maintain goals, rather than simple intellectual ability deficits.^{[5][6]} Therefore, exploring how variables such as self-leadership and goal commitment affect problem-solving ability is essential for developing practical intervention strategies to improve academic achievement.^[1]

In scientific research methodology, replication studies are core processes that enhance the stability and generalizability of research results by confirming whether results derived from specific samples can be consistently reproduced in other environments.^[7,8] Replication studies are broadly categorized into direct replication and conceptual replication. Direct replication involves applying identical research methods and procedures, while conceptual replication maintains core concepts but partially modifies research methods, subjects, and analytical approaches to verify the same theoretical relationships.^[8]

This study is a conceptual replication study based on the research by Lim and Park (2019).^[1] While the previous study included 2nd-3rd year students from multiple institutions (6 universities) and conducted regression analysis, this study targeted all grades (1st-4th year) at a single institution, added academic performance variables, and conducted correlation analysis. These methodological differences are based on the following academic rationale.

First, correlation analysis is optimized for measuring the degree and direction of association between two variables and aligns with the essential purpose of replication studies, which is to confirm the "robustness of associations" rather than causal prediction.^[9] Second, self-leadership and problem-solving ability often form symmetrical relationships that act complementarily in actual competency development processes.^[10] Correlation analysis is suitable for identifying dynamic covariance structures between variables as it allows for variable interchange, whereas regression analysis presupposes unidirectional causal prediction by fixing independent and dependent variables.^[11]

In conclusion, based on recent findings that exposure to leadership skills during nursing student years is related to problem-solving competency,^[12] this study aims to clearly identify correlational structures among core competencies within a changed educational environment and provide foundational data for nursing education.

2. Objective of Study

commitment, and problem-solving ability in nursing students and verify previous research results through conceptual replication. The specific objectives of this study are as follows:

First, to identify the levels of general characteristics, self-leadership, goal commitment, and problem-solving ability in nursing students.

Second, to examine differences in self-leadership, goal commitment, and problem-solving ability according to nursing students' general characteristics (academic year, academic achievement, major satisfaction, etc.).

Third, to identify correlational relationships among self-leadership, goal commitment, and problem-solving ability in nursing students.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Research Design

This study is a descriptive correlational study and conceptual replication study aimed at re-verifying results from Lim and Park's(2019)^[1] study of nursing students at 6 domestic universities in a single institutional environment and conducting comparative analysis of relationships between variables. According to Yang(2014),^[8] conceptual replication studies are processes that verify the reliability and generalizability of research results by partially modifying independent variables, dependent variables, research subjects, and analytical methods while maintaining core theoretical concepts. This study has the following differences compared to the previous multi-institutional study^[1]:

- ①research subjects (multi-institutional vs. single institutional),
- ②grade range (2nd-3rd year vs. 1st-4th year),
- ③additional variables (including academic performance),
- ④analytical methods (regression analysis vs. correlation analysis).

Through these methodological changes, it performs the function of more precisely verifying existing research results.

2. Research Subjects

The subjects of this study were 1st-4th year students enrolled in the nursing department at a university located in U City, with a total of 201 students selected through convenience sampling based on the selection criteria of understanding the study purpose and providing written consent for participation. The sample size for this study followed the calculation basis from the previous study.^[1] The previous study collected data based on a minimum sample size of 166 calculated using G*Power 3.1.9 program with effect size .15, significance level .05, power .95, and 9 predictor variables for multiple regression analysis. The 201 data collected in this study sufficiently exceeded this criterion, meeting the sample size requirement. This was to enhance direct comparability of research results and establish generalization of results by maintaining consistency with previous studies and trusting the calculated procedures, which are core principles of replication studies.

3. Research Instruments

1) Self-Leadership

Self-leadership in this study was measured using an instrument developed by Houghton and Neck (2002)^[13] and modified and supplemented by Kim (2010)^[11] to fit the nursing environment. This instrument consists of 20 items on a 5-point Likert scale, where higher scores indicate higher levels of self-leadership in proactively regulating one's thoughts and behaviors. The instrument's reliability was Cronbach's $\alpha = .87$ in Kim's (2010)^[14] study, and 90 in Lim and Park's(2019)^[11] comparative study. The internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's α) of the self-leadership instrument calculated in this study was confirmed to be .90. This is consistent with the .90 reported in the previous multi-institutional study,^[11] demonstrating that the instrument provides very stable and consistent measurement mechanisms for measuring nursing students' self-leadership even in different research environments.

2) Goal Commitment

Subjects' goal commitment levels were assessed using a scale developed by Klein et al.(2001).^[15] This instrument measures the psychological state of continuously striving and dedicating oneself to achieve established goals, consisting of 5 items on a 5-point Likert scale. The reliability at the time of original instrument development was .83, but was reported as .78 in Lim and Park's (2019.^[11] study. The reliability coefficient in this study was .70.

3) Problem-Solving Ability

Problem-solving ability was measured using an instrument designed by Heppner and Petersen(1982).^[16] and translated into Korean by Hong (2004).^[11] This consists of 32 items on a 6-point Likert scale, where higher scores indicate superior competency in overcoming and resolving obstacles faced in daily life and practice. The reliability in Hong's (2004).^[17]

translation study was .87, and recorded .88 in the previous study by Lim and Park (2019).^[11] The reliability confirmed in this study was also .88, maintaining the same high level.

4. Data Collection Methods

Data collection was conducted from April 14 to May 31, 2024, targeting 1st-4th year students in the nursing department at a university located in U metropolitan city. Data were collected using self-administered questionnaires. Prior to data collection, participating students were provided with explanations about the study's purpose, measurement instruments, and questionnaire items to promote understanding.

5. Ethical Considerations

Before data collection, research subjects were explained about the study's purpose, content, research process, and voluntary participation. They were informed that they could discontinue participation at any time during the survey without any disadvantages. Consent was obtained after explaining that all data would be destroyed after completion of the research report, and then the data were scored.

III. RESULTS

1. Differences in Major Variables According to General Characteristics

Analysis of differences in major variables according to subjects' general characteristics showed significant differences in all three variables according to academic year, academic achievement, interpersonal relationships, and major satisfaction($p < .05$). In grade-level comparison, 2nd-year students showed the lowest scores(2.69±0.31), while 3rd and 4th-year students showed similar levels. In major satisfaction, the 'satisfied' group showed significantly higher scores than the 'dissatisfied' group across all variables (Table 1).

Table 1: Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability According to General Characteristics (N=201).

Characteristics		N(%)	Self-Leadership		Goal Commitment		Problem-Solving Ability	
			M±SD	t/F(p) Scheffé	M±SD	t/F(p) Scheffé	M±SD	t/F(p) Scheffé
Gender	Male	28(13.9)	3.45±.54	.02 (.986)	3.59±.63	-.93 (.185)	3.03±.58	1.77 (.077)
	Female	173(86.1)	3.46±.53		3.70±.52		2.87±.41	
Age	≤21 ^a	60(29.9)	3.41±.49	1.69 (.187)	2.85±.40	.79 (.455)	2.80±.38	5.09 (.007)* a<b
	21-26 ^b	101(50.2)	3.53±.56		2.93±.47		2.97±.46	
	≥27 ^c	40(19.9)	3.59±.62		2.89±.46		3.07±.57	
Academic Year	1학년 ^a	51(25.4)	3.30±.42	3.14 (.027)* b<c,d	3.41±.53	6.56 (.001) a<b,c,d	2.91±.45	5.94 (.001)** b<a,c,d
	2학년 ^b	52(25.9)	3.45±.53		3.76±.39		2.69±.31	
	3학년 ^c	48(23.9)	3.53±.49		3.82±.57		2.99±.45	
	4학년 ^d	50(24.9)	3.60±.63		3.76±.57		2.99±.46	

Academic Achievement	≤3.0 ^a	37(18.4)	3.10±.74	3.66 (.014)* a<d	3.31±.39	3.56** (.008) a<d	2.68±.39	3.53 (.008)** a,b,c<d
	3.0-3.5 ^b	65(32.3)	3.43±.61		3.45±.53		2.91±.47	
	3.6-4.0 ^c	60(29.9)	3.76±.64		3.72±.50		3.09±.39	
	≥4.0 ^d	39(19.4)	3.84±.57		3.84±.57		3.28±.75	
Religion	Yes	95(47.3)	3.48±.59	-.52 (.604)	3.58±.55	-.41 (.681)	2.87±.39	-.52 (.604)
	No	106(52.7)	3.44±.48		3.66±.57		2.91(±48)	
Interpersonal Relationships	Poor ^a	2(1.0)	3.25±.59	8.72 (.001)** a<b	2.40±.00	5.79 (.004)** a<b	2.67±.24	1.60 (.204)
	Average ^b	98(48.8)	3.28±.45		2.78±.42		2.83±.41	
	Good ^c	101(50.2)	3.59±.54		2.97±.43		2.93±.45	
Major Satisfaction	Dissatisfied ^a	11(5.5)	3.11±.57	14.57 (.001)** a<b	2.80±.51	3.51 (.032)* a<b	2.81±.64	3.99 (.020)* a<b
	Average ^b	84(41.8)	3.30±.43		2.81±.40		2.80±.36	
	Satisfied ^c	106(52.7)	3.64±.54		2.97±.44		2.97±.46	

*p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001.

2. Levels of Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability

Analysis of major variable levels showed goal commitment was highest at 3.69±0.54 points, self-

leadership at 3.46±0.55 points, and problem-solving ability at 2.78±0.54 points. Among problem-solving ability sub-areas, self-control recorded the lowest score (2.30±0.62) (Table 2).

Table 2: Levels of Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability (N=201).

Variables	Items	M±SD	Total Score Range	M±SD	Average Range
Self-Leadership	20	69.29±11.07	51~100	3.46±.55	1-5
Behavior-focused strategies	6	20.81±3.18	12~30	3.47±.53	1-5
Natural reward strategies	6	20.11±3.54	9~30	3.35±.59	1-5
Constructive thought strategies	8	28.37±4.35	19~40	3.55±.54	1-5
Goal Commitment	5	18.43±2.70	11~25	3.69±.54	1-5
Problem-Solving Ability	32	92.51±16.51	61~146	2.78±.54	1-6
Confidence	11	34.04±5.93	23~52	3.09±.54	1-6
Approach-avoidance	16	46.99±7.47	34~74	2.94±.47	1-6
Self-control	5	11.48±3.11	5~20	2.30±.62	1-6

3. Correlational Relationships Among Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability

Pearson correlation analysis results showed that self-leadership ($r=.54$, $p<.001$) and goal commitment ($r=.53$,

$p<.001$) had significant positive correlational relationships with problem-solving ability. This indicates that students with higher levels of self-leadership and goal commitment also show higher problem-solving ability in a pattern of concurrent change (Table 3).

Table 3. Correlational Relationships Among Self-Leadership, Goal Commitment, and Problem-Solving Ability (N=201).

Variables	Problem-Solving Ability	
	r	p
Self-Leadership	.54	<.001
Goal Commitment	.53	<.001

IV. DISCUSSION

This study verified the associations between self-leadership, goal commitment, and problem-solving ability in nursing students at a single university through conceptual replication and conducted comparative analysis of competency differences according to academic achievement and major satisfaction among general characteristics. Based on the main issues derived

from the research results, the following discussion is presented.

First, a significant positive correlational relationship ($r=.54$, $p<.001$) was confirmed between nursing students' self-leadership and problem-solving ability. This is consistent with results from the previous study by Lim and Park (2019)^[1] conducted with nursing students from 6 domestic universities and aligns with

research by Lee and Kim (2020)^[18] reporting that self-leadership is related to problem-solving ability. Particularly, the fact that the overall correlational tendency was maintained identically despite the inclusion of 1st-year students who were excluded from the previous study due to insufficient major education completion provides important evidence that the relationship between these two variables can be extended to nursing students in general rather than being limited to specific upper-grade groups.

The fact that these results were identically reproduced within a controlled educational environment of a single institution suggests that the relationship between self-leadership and problem-solving ability is a universal association not constrained by specific curricula or regional characteristics.^[7] Among self-leadership sub-areas, 'constructive thinking strategies' are related to restructuring problem situations as challenges for growth rather than threats, and such cognitive flexibility may be associated with enabling nursing students to exercise critical thinking in complex clinical practice situations to explore optimal alternatives.^[19,10]

Second, a significant positive correlational relationship ($r=.53$, $p<.001$) also appeared between goal commitment and problem-solving ability. This aligns with results that goal commitment is related to patience and concentration in problem-solving processes.^[20] and existing theories that strong psychological commitment to goals concentrates cognitive resources on problem-solving.^[15,21] As nursing students advance in grades, they develop clear goals such as national examination preparation and professional self-concept formation, and higher psychological commitment to these goals may be related to showing solution-oriented attitudes rather than avoidance when facing difficult tasks or clinical practice obstacles.^[22]

Third, analysis results according to general characteristics showed that academic achievement had significant associations with all major variables (self-leadership, goal commitment, problem-solving ability). That is, students with higher academic achievement were confirmed to have higher associations with competencies for self-regulating learning processes, committing to goals, and solving complex problems. This supports the view of existing studies that academic achievement is not simply a result of intellectual performance but forms relationships with individuals' non-cognitive regulatory competencies and learning engagement.^[23,24]

Fourth, grade-level analysis showed that 1st, 3rd, and 4th-year students displayed similar score levels, while 2nd-year students showed a relatively low pattern in problem-solving ability. This is interpreted as reflecting characteristics of the 'grade transition period' that occurs during entry into the nursing major intensification process. The 2nd year is a period when students easily experience academic burden due to rapid expansion of

major foundational knowledge, while the 3rd year is when students undergo role changes from student to prospective healthcare provider through full-scale clinical practice and are given practical responsibilities.^[25] Additionally, results showing that all competency indicators were higher as major satisfaction increased suggest that institutional social support may be related to forming students' autonomous learning attitudes.^[26]

Fifth, the reliability coefficients (Cronbach's α) calculated in this study for self-leadership (.90), goal commitment (.70), and problem-solving ability (.88) were confirmed at levels very similar to or identical with results from the previous multi-institutional study by Lim and Park(2019).^[1] The reconfirmation of high internal consistency of measurement instruments in such replication studies becomes a key indicator proving that this study's results are based on standardized measurement mechanisms rather than chance.^[8]

Therefore, this study has important academic significance in that it enhanced the study's internal validity by reconfirming relationships between variables within a single institution using validated instruments and provided reliable foundational data for identifying factors related to nursing students' competencies.

Comprehensively, this conceptual replication study reconfirmed the stability of the previous research model while securing internal validity as a single-institution study. While multi-institutional studies have high generalizability, institutional environmental differences can act as confounding variables, but this study demonstrated the 'robustness of associations themselves' between variables even under controlled conditions. However, due to the characteristics of a single-institution sample, there are limitations in result generalization, necessitating additional verification in various educational environments in the future.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated through a single-institution conceptual replication study that nursing students' self-leadership and goal commitment have significant positive correlational relationships with problem-solving ability. The final conclusions derived from the research results are as follows.

First, the higher the levels of nursing students' self-leadership and goal commitment, the higher their correlational relationships with problem-solving ability, and these relationships represent universal associations that transcend various grades and academic achievement ranges. Second, among grade-level characteristics, the 2nd year is a period showing relatively low levels of problem-solving ability, with competency levels recovering from the 3rd year onward with clinical practice as a turning point. Third, academic achievement

shows important characteristics with close associations to self-control and self-leadership.

Based on these research results, the following recommendations are made. First, from an educational perspective, since the importance of non-cognitive factors such as self-leadership and goal commitment related to nursing students' problem-solving competency has been reconfirmed, curriculum design considering these factors is necessary. Support measures for 2nd-year students and underachieving students experiencing academic difficulties are particularly urgent. Second, from a practical perspective, to enhance students' goal commitment, consideration can be given to creating autonomous learning environments where students can establish and reflect on their own goals during project-based learning (PjBL) or simulation education. Third, from a research perspective, since this study has limitations as a single-institution cross-sectional study, future research should include additional conceptual replication studies targeting multiple institutions and longitudinal studies tracking what associations changes in self-leadership and goal commitment show with actual clinical performance changes.

*** This study was supported by the 2024 Choonhae Health Sciences University Research Support.**

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